

CONSUMERS ATTITUDES TOWARDS THE ORGANIC PRODUCTS IN COIMBATORE CITY

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Introduction:

Agriculture is the principal source of livelihood for more than 40 percent of the population of this State. Agriculture provides wage goods required by the non-agricultural sectors and raw materials for the industrial sector. Ratcheting up the growth of the economy would be possible provided the agriculture sector fares well on a sustained basis. A good performance of the agriculture sector is view as an effective instrument for attainment of inclusive economic growth and poverty reduction. The State achieved an all-time high record production of 10.1 million tones of food-grains during 2011-12 and received the Krishi Karman Award from the Government of India. Tamil Nadu performed well ahead of other major States in terms of productivity of important crops. It ranked second in the productivity of paddy next only to Punjab and came first in the yield of maize, millet and oilseeds. Millet is also one of the important food products, which was regularly consumed in all families in the olden days.

The productivity of millet in Tamil Nadu was almost double of what was obtained at the national level. Organic products are highly useful to all of us to maintain good health and physic. Irrespective of the age, millet helps to the human free from number diseases. The elder people in the family prefer to consume eatables prepared with the help of millet. The middle age group and the younger hesitate to take millet food. In some of the area still now in all family they used to food prepared by using millets. In the urban area the consumption of millet is considerably reduced. If we asked the young people they simply say no for taking the millet food products. Further many of the children and younger do not know about the millets and its varieties

The development in communication system found new era during 1990s and 2000. Media heavily attracted the public particularly by the advertisement given in the television. In most of the families, preparation of foods by using of paddy rice, wheat powder and mydha powder is preferred by all family members. Further utilization of domestic items like mixer, grinder and juicer, induction stove made the human being sophisticated and do not involve in any hard work by the women in all family. They simply add some flavours and masala powders to increase the taste of the food. So the usage of millet is unknown to most of the members in the families in the urban areas. As the millet is cultivated mostly in wet land in the raining season and there is limited use of manures. Millet is considered as the natural food and adds energy to the human body. In all situations, all of us face some of the disease in our body. Sometimes it leads to lose of lives to many people and family. When we approach the physician they give advice to consume the food items prepared with millets instead of the modern foods. In reality the people do not prepare the food items by using organic products. The children in most of the family do not know the organic products and their uses likewise the young age male and female members in the family do not prefer the organic products. This paves way for getting diseases at the earlier stage. Further after the age of 40 most of the people face any one serious disease.

Statement of the Problem:

In modern scenario most of the public attracted with modern food items in which more volume of masala powders and artificial flavors are added to increase the taste of the food items. Irrespective of the age, color and region all the people prefer these types of modern foods. Further, due to the consumption of these food items even in the younger age people are suffering from anyone of the serious diseases. More amounts are spent towards the medical expenses. Spending money is not the serious matter but the suffering by all human beings is questionable and to be given due attention to eliminate this issue. The elder people and well wishers of the society speak frequently about the causes of modern food items. But nobody is ready to hear the words of such persons. When we go hospitals, we all experience this problem. In all hospital more crowds is waiting to consult the doctors. They are suffering from various diseases. In olden days it was not like that. Our elders had strengthened body and good physic. They led their life simply with happy. At present the entire situation is changed. Most of us used to have some tablet and drugs continuously. When the individual meet the doctors for recovery, he or she feels about the causes of consuming food prepared by using other food grains like paddy rice, packed foods. The public should know all the problems of modern food items and its causes to the health. The young generation should be safeguarded from using of modern food items particularly eatables in which more flavors used to add the taste. Government and NGOs should take initiatives to create awareness about the serious issues and problems from modern foods. As most of us use the modern food items frequently we are

inviting the serious diseases knowing or unknowingly to ourselves. The lifetime of all human beings is decreasing gradually year by year.

Significance of the Study:

Companies are offering their product with view to market their products and earn more profit. Hence, they give various types of advertisement, which normally attract the customers and consumers. However, no effort is taken by anybody to create awareness about the organic products, further until now nobody is taking care about the health of young generation. The students are the main stream of the future India. They must know the causes of food prepared by using other food grain like paddy rice, packed foods to the human health. This can be possible by focusing the consumers' attitude about organic products in the study area. Students and younger generation are to be educated and next generation customer of the organic product to raise the need for this research to focus the students' particularly young and energetic public. Hence the study about the organic products is inevitable and to be a needed one.

Objectives of the Study:

The following are the objectives framed for the successful completion of the research work.

- To know the awareness of the customer towards the characteristics of organic products.
- To evaluate the willingness to pay for organic products
- To study the factors to be considered by the consumer while purchasing organic products
- To analyze the average relationship between demographic variables and their attitudes towards the organic products.
- To identify the problems of the consumers in using the organic products.
- To offer recommendations to the needy to safeguard the health and maintain good physic for the future generation

Research Methodology:

Research Design: Descriptive research was conducted in this study to make the research effective and useful to the needy.

Collection of Data: Both the primary and secondary data were collected in this research work

Primary Data: Primary data was collected from the sample respondents from the population by way preparing a questionnaire. The questionnaire was prepared with the guidance of the experts in the relevant field. Necessary corrections were made in the questionnaire to complete the research work successfully.

Secondary Data: Secondary data was collected from the journals and magazine published in the related topics.

Sample Design:

The sample selection was made from the study area i.e. from the Coimbatore City. The population for the study is general public of the study area. As the food prepared by using other food grains like paddy rice, packed foods are liked more by the younger generation and the students, most of the sample respondents are below the age group of 45 years and only meager amount of respondents were selected from the age group above 45 years. Further, the sample respondents consist of male and female respondents. They further were classified in to students, businessmen, government employees and employees working in private industries and also the labour. 100 respondents were selected from the study area for the purpose getting survey.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Showing the Gender of the Respondents

S.No	Gender	Frequency	Percent
1	Male	67	67
2	Female	33	33
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table it is understood that among 100 respondents 67 percent of the respondents are male while the remaining 33 percent of the respondents are female.

Table 2: Showing the Age of the Respondents

S.No	Age	Frequency	Percent
1	18-24 years	14	14
2	25-31 years	41	41
3	32-39 years	27	27
4	40 years and above	18	18
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table reveals that among 100 respondents 41 percent of the respondents are belonged to the age group of 25-31 years. 27 percent of the respondents are in the age group of 32-39 years, 18 percent of the respondents are in the age group of 40 years and above while the remaining 14 of the respondents are belonged to the age group of 18-24 years

Table 3: Showing the Education of the Respondents

S.No	Education	Frequency	Percent
1	Up to 10th std	23	23
2	Up to 12th std	37	37
3	Degree	28	28
4	Professional and others	12	12
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table brings an eye view that among 100 respondents 37 percent of the respondents have studied up to 12th standard, 28 percent of the respondents are degree holders, 23 percent of the respondents have studied up to 10th standard and the remaining 12 percent of the respondents have studied professional courses.

Table 4: Showing the Monthly Income of the Respondents

S.No	Monthly income	Frequency	Percent
1	Rs.5000 -9000	23	23
2	Rs.9001-13000	34	34
3	Rs.13001-17000	30	30
4	above Rs.17000	13	13
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table it is inferred that among 100 respondents 34 percent of the respondents get a monthly income between Rs.9001-13000, 30 percent of the respondents earn between Rs.13001-17000 as their monthly income, 23 percent of the respondents receive Rs.5000-9000 as their monthly income whereas the remaining 13 percent of the respondents get above Rs.17000 as their monthly income.

Findings:

- Majority of the respondents (67%) are Male
- Most of the respondents (41%) are in the age group of 25-31 years
- Considerable portion of the respondents (37%) have studied up to 12th standard
- Majority of the respondents get a monthly income between Rs. 9001-13000.
- Most of the respondents (57%) are satisfied with the nutrition content in the organic products
- Considerable portion of the respondents (63%) informed that the young generations are not aware of the uses of organic products.
- Majority of the respondents informed that (59%) in the recent past the price of the organic products are comparatively high.
- Major portion of the respondents (72%) are satisfied with the availability of organic products.
- Most of the respondents informed (67%) that the sellers are not providing discount to the organic products as like in other products.
- Most of the respondents (45%) agree that the demand for organic products is going on increasing nowadays.
- Majority of the respondents (61%) conveyed that the organic products have medicinal character to maintain good health.

Suggestions:

- Some of the respondents (53.3%) informed that the young generations are not aware of the uses of organic products. Hence, the parents and elders should create awareness about the organic products to all the younger regarding the nutrition available in the organic products.
- Some of the respondents (43.2%) informed that the price of the organic products is high when compared with other products. The government and the businesspersons, who involved in organic products, should take initiatives if possible to reduce the price of the organic products.
- It is found that majority of the respondents (63.9) conveyed that availability of traditional and an organic product is comparatively low as like other products. So effort must be taken to make availability of organic products in all shops which in turn can be bought by all the consumers.
- Majority of the respondents (28.8%) informed that the young generation should not bother about the causes of fast food items particularly to the health. Hence the government should take initiatives to create awareness regarding the issues of using fast food items. The NGO should play a vital role in this regard.
- Most of the respondents informed that the young women who got married do not know the method to prepare food by using the organic items like Raggi, Maise, millet etc. Hence, the elders in the house should make them aware of making food items by using the organic products.

Conclusion:

For both men and women good physic is required to support the family members and their wards. Further to live-long life we have to maintain good health without any serious diseases. Then only the human being can live to a normal period, which helps to grow their wards. So, that it is necessary to have cautious about our health. It is reported that most of the people nowadays affected by serious disease because of their food habit particularly by using fast food items. Hence, every one of us should think about our future and the life of our younger generation and try to make all the people use the organic food products for making their food regularly and lead a peaceful life with minimum curable diseases to make India having the healthiest citizens to lead their life happily and bring betterment to the individual, group and to the society as a whole.

References:

1. M. Wier, L.M. Anderson, Demand for organic foods-attitudes, values and purchasing behaviors, Newslett. Danish Res. Center Farm. 2 (2003) 1–3.
2. M.-F. Chen, Consumer attitudes and purchase intentions in relation to organic foods in Taiwan: moderating effects of food-related personality traits, Food Qual. Prefer. 18 (2007) 1008–1021.
3. S. Zakowska-Biemans, Consumers values and motives regarding organic food products in Poland, in: Proceedings of the 2nd Scientific Conference of the International Society of Organic Agriculture Research ISOFAR, vol. 2, Modena, Italy, June 18–20, 2008, pp. 506–509.
4. M. Kristensen, L.F. Ostergaard, U. Halekoh, H. Jorgensen, Ch. Lauridsen, K. Brandt, S. Bugel, Effect of plant cultivation methods on content of major and trace elements in foodstuffs and retention in rats, J. Sci. Food Agric. 88 (2008) 2161–2172.
5. K. Woese, D. Lange, C. Boess, K.W. Bogl, A comparison of organically and conventionally grown foods-results of a review of the relevant literature, J. Sci. Food Agric. 74 (1997) 281–293.
6. V. Worthington, Nutritional quality of organic versus conventional fruits, vegetables, and grains, J. Altern. Complement. Med. 7 (2001) 161–173.